

Liquid line of descent and sulfide saturation of the Paleoproterozoic komatiites in Central Lapland Greenstone Belt, Finland

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A suite of Paleoproterozoic komatiites extends over hundreds of kilometers from the northern Norway to the eastern part of the Central Lapland Greenstone Belt (CLGB) in the northern Finland. Many of these komatiites show close spatial relationship with sulfur-bearing black schists and anhydrites, which makes them interesting targets for base and noble metal sulfide deposits. The Kevitsa and Sakatti Cu-Ni(-PGE) sulfide deposits are also closely spatiotemporally associated with these komatiites and sedimentary rocks. Recent studies have evaluated the potential parental melt composition of the komatiites [1,2], but the liquid line of descent remains unconstrained. The closed-system liquid line of descent is a useful baseline to unravel geochemical signals related to crystal accumulation, assimilation, and post-magmatic alteration. Furthermore, it can be used to approximate sulfur content at sulfide saturation (SCSS), which, in turn, can be used to predict the onset of sulfide precipitation.

We use MELTS software to define the parental melt composition and the liquid line of descent for the Paleoproterozoic komatiites of the CLGB. The parental melt composition is back-calculated from a well-characterized natural komatiitic dyke that represents a melt composition [1,2]: the equilibrium olivine is first defined using MELTS and then a small increment of that olivine is added to the melt. We repeat this procedure until reaching a melt composition that is in equilibrium with the most forsteritic olivine population identified from the Kevitsa and Sakatti intrusions. We conduct fractional crystallization simulations with MELTS to determine the liquid line of descent for the back-calculated parental melt. The simulation results are validated by comparing them with previously published geochemical data from the natural CLGB komatiites. Although these komatiites are variably altered, their main geochemical features conform well with the simulation results, especially in the case of the least mobile major elements.

We use the liquid line of descent calculated by MELTS together with the SCSS model of Smythe et al. [3] to estimate how SCSS varies in the CLGB komatiites that experienced closed-system fractional crystallization. Based on the results, we estimate the onset of closed-system sulfide saturation and characterize the associated geochemical features such as Ni content in olivine. Clear deviations from the predicted closed-system behaviour in the natural rock record could indicate that open-system processes affected sulfide saturation. The defined liquid line of descent will be used to develop more complex computational and laboratory simulations that focus on open-system processes, such as assimilation and magmatic recharge.

References:

- [1] Nicklas et al. (2019) *Geochim. Cosmochim. Acta* 250:49-75
- [2] Puchtel et al. (2020) *Chem Geol* 554:1-23
- [3] Smythe et al. (2017) *Am Min* 102: 795-803